

Structural Features in Girish Karnad's *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*

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...dreaming is not dishonourable. My master, Tipu Sultan, dreamt.

Kirmani (Two Plays: 2005:16)

When Girish Karnad was commissioned by BBC to write a radio play to celebrate the Fiftieth Anniversary of Indian Independence, he immediately thought of Tipu Sultan, who according to him, was one of the most 'politically perceptive and tragic figures in modern Indian history' (Karnad 2005:4). To Karnad, Tipu was a 'politically perceptive' and 'tragic figure' for he had envisioned a strong and united Mysore but could not fulfill his vision. And when Karnad's mentor A. K. Ramanujan told him about the secret records of Tipu's dreams in the form of a diary, Karnad decided to use it to tell the story of Tipu through his dreams. Luckily, Karnad got his hands on the copy of this diary at the Regenstein library of the University of Chicago. Karnad wrote the radio play, *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*, which was broadcast on 15 August, 1997. The published version, however, has been completely rewritten for the stage performance. The present paper aims to study the structural features of *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*.

Karnad employs two ways of presenting a story in his plays: scenic presentation (the principle of succession) and narrative mediation (principle of mediation). Both the methods are sometimes combined or used in isolation. In Karnad's history plays, the mediating communication system is absent. It means that the story is presented according to the principle of succession. The presentation follows the order of actions and events as they occur in the story. There is a quick succession of scenes and each successive scene presents the successive phase of the story. There is no overlap of actions or events. There is no use of flashbacks. That means the action phases of the story do not coincide chronologically as they are completely separate. However, one of the most important features they share is the identity of the central figure. They

are also interlinked by a number of recurrent thematic motifs, such as the quest for the self. Sometimes these phases are coordinated according to the principle of juxtaposition. Then these phases coincide chronologically and create parallel phases of action. For example, the duo of Azam and Aziz in *Tughlaq* who appear in shallow scenes of the play and exploit all the opportunities created by the flawed decisions of the Sultan. Their story runs parallel to the eventful narrative of Tughlaq. They make a mockery of Tughlaq's idealism and enter into the deep scene as being on par with him at the end of the play.

In his non-history plays and *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*, Karnad conspicuously combines both the techniques of presentations. Manfred Pfister describes how both these techniques can be combined to achieve higher impact on the audience. To him, overall there are three steps involved in the presentation of action or chain of events. Firstly there is a 'verbally mediated anticipatory phase'. In this phase, the main action is introduced or announced. Second is the 'scenic realization of the action'. And thirdly, there is the 'verbally mediated retrospective narrative' to recapitulate or inform the audience about the action. These three steps are not used in all the plays. They can be combined or used in isolation. And the anticipatory or retrospective narratives need not be restricted to the narration of a single character. The action can be anticipated or recapitulated through the speeches of many different characters (209). This method is well illustrated in the following discussion of three layered structure. The tripartite structure of anticipation (A), scenic realization (SR) and retrospection (R) corresponds to the three layers in Karnad's plays. The narrative figures in these plays (The Sutradhara, the Bhagavata, the Story, the King, Arvasu, the Priest, the Announcer, and the Choric Characters) present the anticipatory speech and introduce the main action. The action is, then, realized scenically (i.e. through direct presentation). These figures appear at the end to recapitulate the action happened lately through their retrospective narrative mediation.

As stated above, the source text of *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan* is the record of Tipu's dream kept by himself in his own handwriting. The Preface to the record informs us about many details about it and its discovery. It was discovered by Colonel Kirkpatrick in Tipu's bed chamber while sifting through the palace for many valuable objects and documents. The Munshi, Habibullah, was witness to the discovery of this manuscript. Tipu had kept secrecy about the

existence of such record though the Munshi had got hint of it. Afterwards, on 23 April, 1800, Major Alexander Beatson presented this diary or ‘resister’ (as it is always referred) in the name of the Marquis Wellesley to Hugh Inglis, Chairman of the court of the Directors of the East India Company. The dreams and other related notes had been written on the first thirty- two pages of the register and again on eleven pages at the end. Many pages had been left blank in between. The size of the register is 7 7/8 inches by 5 7/8 inches (The Dreams: 7-9). The register is not the record of all Tipu Sultan’s dreams as he did not record all of them but only those he thought worth recording. His first recorded dream dated 1785 and the last 1798 covering the period of thirteen years. They are thirty seven in number and he had provided some of them with his interpretations. Majority of these dreams deal with his wars against the British and their allies (9-12). His dreams are predominated by the thought of liberating and protecting the nation from foreign powers especially the British. Mahmud Husain says:

‘From a perusal of this register it becomes clear that his hours of sleep were as devoted to the cause of freedom as the hours while he was awake’ (Dreams: 15).

Girish Karnad has incorporated four of Tipu’s dreams and invented one dream himself i.e. the dream of Haider Ali’ Visit in *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*. However, the play is not just an enactment of the dreams. Karnad has also showed some of the important happenings in Tipu’s life in between these dreams. He has used the choric characters to present his point of view and to inform us about the happenings after the death of Tipu Sultan. The choric characters guide us by providing a frame for understanding the context of Tipu’s dreams. They start with description of the ghastly scene of Tipu’s death. The British soldiers find out Tipu’s dead body and treat it very badly. Then Kirmani recalls his last meeting with Tipu and how he got to know about the record of Tipu’s dream. Tipu also gave him the record of his last dream which Kirmani presents at the end of the play. The rest of the dreams are presented by Tipu himself. Karnad has presented the dreams of Tipu Sultan as they appear in the record without making any change as such. The Extraordinary Idols, the White Elephant from China, a Woman in Man’s Dress, Tipu’s last dream – The Expulsion of the English are taken from the diary. Girish Karnad’s only addition (interpolation) is the dream describing Haider Ali’s visit.

About the form, the play was initially conceived for the medium called radio. But the written version is put in the form of ‘Dream inset’. ‘Dream inset’ refers to a dramatic piece in which a dream of a character is embedded. It is like any other action sequence or event in a play. The only difference is that it is imagined by one of the characters of the play. It is either presented dramatically or mediated through narration. The latter is the most common and easiest form of presentation. The dream soliloquy is one of the activities in which dream sequence is presented in both ways. The character speaks while dreaming. The act of dreaming is shown but the content of the dream is mediated narratively through soliloquy. In dream inset, on the contrary, the dream of the character is performed and ‘the stage is transformed into the inner chamber of the dreamer’s mind’ (Pfister 220). However, the transition between the embedded dream sequence and the ‘primary dramatic level’ of the play is clearly marked with certain indicators to facilitate the understanding of the audience. Pfister underlines the following characteristic features of dream inset.

1. Dream inset is embedded as subordinate sequence in a play
2. The embedding and embedded sequences are closely connected by ‘sets of clear thematic and situative equivalents and by the fact that the dreamer appears as the active subject of the dream’.
3. Sometimes, the subordinate level of dream sequence outweighs the level of primary or ‘superordinate sequence’ in quantitative terms. As a result the latter just serves the purpose of a dramatic framework which introduces and concludes the dream sequence.
4. Hence, the present distinction of subordinate and superordinate only stresses the ‘ontological relationship’ between the two and not the ‘dramatic focalization’ which shows the ‘theatrical or thematic’ supremacy of one element over another.
5. In extreme cases, there is no ‘superordinate framework’ but only the all encompassing dream sequence. For example, Strindberg’s Dream Play. In this case the dreamer serves as the implied author and the receiver with no one to introduce him.
6. However, in most of the plays in which the dreams of the character are embedded, there is a clear dividing line separating the primary framework and the subordinate level of the dream inset. For example, Karnad’s The Dreams of Tipu Sultan.

7. These plays prepare the audience for the dreams to be imagined by the concerned character by way of his utterances. Sometimes the characters discuss the dreams of another character.
8. The scenes follow each other in rapid succession. It is done by shifting location on stage and of lighting.
9. The dream inset serves variety of functions as ‘characterization, plot motivation and thematic mirroring to implicit references to the theatrical medium itself’.
10. The relationship between the dreamer and the dream inset is like that of the implied author and the text (220-223).

The Dream of Tipu Sultan has the following features of Dream inset. Firstly, dreams of Tipu Sultan are embedded as subordinate sequence in a play. The embedding and embedded sequences are closely connected by ‘sets of clear thematic and situative equivalents and by the fact that the dreamer appears as the active subject of the dream’ (ibid). The subordinate level of dream sequence outweighs the level of primary or ‘superordinate sequence’ in quantitative terms. As a result the latter just serves the purpose of a dramatic framework which introduces and concludes the dream sequence. There is a clear dividing line separating the primary framework and the subordinate level of the dream inset. The Choric characters discuss the dreams of Tipu Sultan. The scenes follow each other in rapid succession. Here, it shows the influence of Company Nataka on the form of the play as it is found in all Karnad’s history plays. The relationship between the dreamer and the dream inset is like that of the implied author and the text as it is seen in the interpretation of some dreams offered by Tipu himself.

As mentioned earlier, *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan* does not have the episodic structure normally employed in Girish Karnad’s plays. According to Aparna Dharwadkar, the play has ‘three-layered structure’ found in his non-history plays. The first two layers are at the beginning and ending of the play presenting the memory of the choric characters; and the third layer is that of Tipu’s dreams which are ‘partly narrated and partly enacted’ (CI:VII: xxvi). The choric characters provide the frame for the dream inset that is embedded in the play. They form the first layer and Tipu, the second in which is embedded the third layer of Tipu’s dream. It is represented diagrammatically in the following way:

Three Layered Structure of *The Dreams of Tipu Sultan*

The Dreams of Tipu Sultan also has a tripartite structure of anticipation, scenic realization and retrospection. The choric characters, Hussain Ali Kirmani, the historian and Colin Machenzie, the oriental scholar, discuss and present some important happenings in Tipu's life and five of his dreams. Their expository dialogue reveal the objective and subject matter of the play i.e. knowing the 'other side' (Two plays: 8), the Indian side, of the history about Tipu Sultan and his destruction. This is the phase of anticipation.

Tipu Sultan gave Kirmani an envelope in their last meeting. After the death of Tipu Sultan, Kirmani opened the envelope containing a paper on which he had recorded his last dream. This narrative is followed by the scene in which the British soldiers are trying to locate the dead body of Tipu. They want to be assured that they have really succeeded in killing him. Finally they get foot on his dead body. They then enter the city, plundering and looting as they walk. Kirmani sums up it thus:

'So the Tiger of Mysore had at last been hunted down. And the first salutation he received from the hunters was to have his whiskers chopped off' (ibid: 15).

The choric characters comment on the happenings and provide fillers to further the action to the next scene. Mackenzie wants Kirmani to write about Tipu's embassy to Mauritius, the 'Malarctic Adventure' (ibid). But the latter had rejected the existence of such adventure though in the following scenes there are references to such embassy and Tipu's attempt to woo the French.

Through the choric characters we learn about the discovery of the 'dairy' containing Tipu's dreams. Munshi Habibullah found it and according to Kirmani, he should have destroyed it. The diary was secretly kept by Tipu; even his close confidants were not aware about the existence of any such record. It was hidden under his pillow. '*It was sacred, personal*' (17). To the British, it was just an 'inconsequential conversational piece' and a perfect gift for the Chairman of the Court of Directors of the 'Honourable' East India Company. There are many blank pages in the dairy. Tipu must have recorded only the dreams which had spoken to him. But

to the rationalist Mackenzie, the British are not interested in such record of dreams as it is historically insignificant. The anticipation phase is, thus, extended further to provide the necessary context for the understanding of Tipu's dreams.

Tipu Sultan presents his five dreams: the Extraordinary Idols, the White Elephant from China, A Woman in Man's Attire, Haider Ali's Visit and the Expulsion of the Englishman. The enactment of Tipu's dreams forms the phase of scenic realization.

In the phase of retrospection, Mackenzie tells us that after the death of Tipu Sultan, the tigers in the palace were killed and the mechanical tiger was sent to London. To Mornington, it sent a warning to other princes of the consequences of inviting foreign powers against the English. Arthur Wellesley succeeded in getting more responsibilities from the Duke of Wellington to Prime Minister of England. Tipu Sultan's sons were taken out of Seringapatam and sent to Calcutta to be kept under surveillance. The English too seized the Maratha power within the next twenty years. Tipu's predictions but not his dreams that finally proved correct, according to Kirmani. The postscripts narrate the fate of Tipu's sons and families of Maharajas:

When India became independence in 1947, the families of maharajas who had bowed and scraped before the British masters were granted sumptuous privy purses by the Government of India while the descendants of Tipu Sultan were left to rot in the slums of Calcutta (65).

The play is thus structured like a presentation of Tipu's dreams in a systematic manner. The dreams are introduced and concluded by the Choric Characters in both the phase of anticipation and retrospection respectively. The dreams are presented in both ways scenic realization and narrative mediation by Tipu himself except the last dream that was recalled by Kirmani.

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